

Studies in Ferric Hydroxide Sol: Part I. Changes in pH, electrical conductance and chloride ion concentration during slow coagulation by Electrolytes

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The changes in pH, electrical conductivity and chloride ion concentration of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol observed during the slow coagulation in presence of KCl , K_2SO_4 and potassium citrate have been studied in comparison with that of the aqueous solution of ferric chloride acting as the dispersion medium (the so-called intermicellar liquid), being of the same conductance as that of the sol. On adding the electrolyte, the maximum changes in conductance, pH and in chloride ion concentration have been observed to occur immediately indicating that the phenomenon like ion-exchange, adsorption or surface neutralisation during the slow coagulation are instantaneous processes.

In continuation of our previous publications¹⁻³ on the studies in negative sols, we have extended our experiments on the changes in pH, conductance and chloride ion concentration of ferric hydroxide sol during slow coagulation by three different electrolytes, viz., KCl , K_2SO_4 and potassium citrate. The interesting results are recorded in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol was prepared by adding concentrated ammonium carbonate solution to a solution of FeCl_3 with constant stirring until the precipitate just ceased to dissolve. The precipitate of ferric hydroxide was then dissolved by adding just the sufficient quantity of 5% FeCl_3 . The sol was then dialysed in a parchment paper bag against running distilled water.

Experimental procedures for the determination of the specific conductance of the sol, and the amount of electrolyte required to coagulate the sol in one hour and also the changes in pH, were exactly the same as recorded in our previous communications. The chloride ion concentration was determined by using an Ag/AgCl electrode against colomel half-cell.

The sol was mixed with the known amount of the electrolyte required to coagulate it in one hour and its conductivity, pH and chloride ion concentration were determined at different intervals of time. The same was repeated by mixing the intermicellar liquid with same amount of the electrolyte. Curves were plotted for the conductivities, pH and chloride ion concentrations with time in both the cases. The concentration of the electrolytes added were 0.1 M KNO_3 , 0.0044 M K_2SO_4 and 0.002 M potassium citrate per litre of the sol.

1. Chaturvedi & Bhattacharya, *this Journal*, 1954 31, 132.
2. Bansal et al., *Koll. Z. Polymers*, 1963, 189, 147.
3. Bansal et al., *J.I.C.S.*, 1963, 40, 1029.

DISCUSSION

The observation on the changes in conductance, chloride ion concentration and pH of the sol with respect to the intermicellar liquid, after addition of electrolytes, during the slow coagulation are noted below :

1. On adding the electrolyte to the sol, the chloride ion concentration shoots up instantaneously where after it shows no variation during further period of coagulation (*vide* curves 7, 8 and 9). But in the case of the intermicellar liquid, the chloride ion concentration does not show any change on the addition of the electrolyte (curve 10). The increase in chloride ion concentration in the sol on the addition of different electrolytes are in the following order :

Citrate > Sulphate > Nitrate

which is also the order of the valency of these ions, The increase in chloride ion concentration is due to the displacement of chloride ions from the diffuse outer layer.

2. The pH of the sol instantaneously shoots up to the maximum on the addition of the electrolytes and then shows a very gradual fall during the further period of slow coagulation (*vide* curves 4, 5 and 6). The intermicellar liquid shows almost no change in pH on addition of the electrolytes except that with time there is also a gradual fall (*vide* curves 4a, 5a and 6a).

The association and dissociation tendencies in a sol are at equilibrium and when the anions are introduced in $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol, the electric charge on the colloidal particle decreases by neutralisation and a partly neutralized surface is formed. It has a tendency to adsorb H_3O^+ from the system. The increase in pH with the addition of electrolyte may be due to this adsorption of H_3O^+ ions on the partly neutralized surface of the sol particles causing thereby, an increase in the OH^- ion concentration of the medium. The gradual fall of pH afterwards may be attributed to the slow hydrolysis of the FeCl_3 present with the sol as stabilizing electrolyte as has also been observed in the case of the intermicellar liquid alone itself.

3. On adding the electrolyte, the conductivity instantaneously shoots up both in the case of the sol and the intermicellar liquid; yet there is an appreciable difference in the conductivity of the coagulating sol (sol + Electrolyte), and the intermicellar liquid having the same amount of the electrolyte. The conductivity of the sol the coagulating electrolyte is less than that of the intermicellar liquid containing the same amount of electrolyte in the case of KNO_3 and K_2SO_4 but reverse has been observed with potassium citrate (*vide* curves 1, 1a, 2, 2a and 3, 3a).

The conductivity of the sol becomes less than that of the intermicellar liquid both having the same amount of electrolyte which may be due to the following causes :—

1. The thickness of the double layer decreases whereby the electrostatic attraction between the fixed and diffuse parts of the double layer is increased, resulting in a decrease in the mobility of the micelles.

2. Adsorption of the hydroxonium ions on the partly neutralized surface of the sol

particles results in a decrease in concentration of hydrogen ion (in the form of H_3O^+ ions) which are more conducting than the OH^- ions.

FIG. 1

With potassium citrate the conductivity of the sol is greater than that of the intermicellar liquid. This accounts for the fact that along with adsorption of hydroxonium ion and the decrease of the thickness of double layer which have been accounted for the fall of the conductivity of the sol particles, there may be some surface reaction with citrate ions resulting in the formation of some compound (complex) which on hydrolysis may yield ions of greater ionic mobility to increase the conductivity of the sol.

On addition of the electrolyte, the maximum changes in conductance, pH and in Cl^- ion concentration have been observed to occur immediately indicating that the phenomenon like ion exchange, adsorption or surface neutralisation during slow coagulation is an instantaneous process.

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FIG. 2

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